

Exploring of a New Natural Fiber Composite — Ramie Fabric / UP Composite

H.M. Wang¹, Y.Q. Sun¹, J.B. Wang¹, Y.T. Guan¹, S.R. Zheng² and M.L. Sun²

¹*Northwest Institute of Textile Sci. & Tech., Xi'an, 710048, China*

²*Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an, 710072, China*

SUMMARY: Ramie, a renewable natural fiber abundantly produced in China (three harvests a year), not only has the comparable advantages to other bast fibers (flax, hemp, jute and sisal etc.) but also is very clean after fiber preparation. In this study, two kinds of ramie fabric (with size and without size) were chosen for reinforcement in composites respectively. The influence of fabric surface conditions and fiber volume fraction on the mechanical properties (tensile, bend and shear,) is investigated. Preliminary results show that the composites reinforced by the ramie cloth without size have better mechanical properties than those of by the cloth with size. No significant influence of fiber volume fraction on the mechanical properties of the composites was found. SEM investigations demonstrated that the composite reinforced by ramie fabric without size has better adhesion between fiber and matrix than that of by fabric with size.

KEYWORDS: natural fiber composites, ramie fabric, unsaturated polyester, mechanical properties, size, fractographic observation

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the ecological concern has led to an increasing interest in exploring and using environment friendly materials. Natural materials become important candidates. In the international composite community, using natural fiber as reinforcement or filler in civil application has attracted more and more researchers in Asia, Europe and Oceania [1-7]. The natural fibers they used in their investigations were mainly from the lignocellulose fibers: jute, flax and sisal. In comparison with the conventional glass fiber, these vegetable fibers have many advantages. They are biodegradable and no or much less harm to the environment. They have lower density, much lower price, proper mechanical properties, and so on. [8]

In addition to the three nature fibers, another vegetable fiber — ramie fiber is worth exploring, which has not received enough attention yet. The ramie, also called as China Grass which are mainly grown in China — a perennial shrub, can provide abundant resource for the ramie fiber (three harvests a year). Ramie fiber has the same advantages as the three natural fibers do, and is even superior to the jute and flax fiber when comprehensive mechanical properties are all taken into account. Therefore, ramie fiber used as the reinforcement or filler of composites will be of great potential both ecologically and economically. On the other hand, with decreasing the demand for ramie fiber as traditional textile raw material, it is necessary to look for new nontextile applications to preserve the abundant ramie resource through make full use of them. Current work attempts to explore a new composite — ramie fiber composite material.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials

The composite system chosen for this study was ramie fabric / UP system. The reinforcement was ramie fabrics. The matrix was a thermoset resin unsaturated polyester (UP). The ramie fabric supplied by Hunan Dongting Ramie Textile Company, China, was plain woven cloth. The weaving pattern is 36 Nm \times 36 Nm \times 244 Numbers / 10cm \times 244 Numbers / 10cm as shown in Fig.1. The fabrics with two different surface conditions were used for composite panels making. One was “as-received” with the size for textile process, directly from the supplier. The other was desized in a heated chemical solution (NaOH 15g/L, 90°C and 50 min). The mechanical properties of these two kinds of cloth were measured as shown in table1:

Fig. 1 The weave pattern of the ramie fabric

Table1 The mechanical properties of ramie fabric with different surface conditions

Cloth	Direction	Tensile strength Mpa	Elongation (%)
With size	Warp	223.51	10.44
	Weft	270.75	5.92
Without size	Warp	196.65	12.76
	weft	259.05	6.84

The unsaturated polyester (UP) made in Xi’an Resin Factory was used as matrix. The tensile properties of its mould were tested as shown in table 2:

Table 2 The tensile properties of the UP mould

Cast Temperature (°C)	Tensile Strength (Mpa)	Young’s Mudulus (Gpa)
60	42.15	1.86
80	47.88	2.11
100	38.64	2.15

Panel Fabrication

The composite panels were made using sheets of the ramie cloth and UP liquid. First, ramie cloth was cut into as big as the mould and dried in an oven at 105°C for 1 hour. The layers of the sheet and UP liquid pasted on the sheet by hand were alternatively stacked. Second, the impregnation was achieved by applying heat (60° or 80°C) and pressure (1.0Mpa) for about 2 hours. The composites obtained after cooling had a certain thickness depending on the fiber volume fraction.

Mechanical Tests

Tensile tests on the ramie composites were performed on a electric tensile machine, according to GB1447-83 standard, with the rectangular shape of specimens (250mm× 25mm×2mm). The bend tests were carried out on a testing machine for materials, according to GB1449-83, with the rectangular shape of specimens (40mm×15mm×2mm). The shear tests were performed on a testing machine for materials, according to GB-3357-82. The specimen dimensions are 20mm×6mm×2mm.

Fractographic Observation

The fracture surfaces of tested specimens were subjected to observation in scanning electron microscope (SEM). The specimen surfaces were sputter coated with gold, and then were viewed in a HITACHI S 570 SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Influence of Interface Conditions

The results of the tests show that the mechanical properties of the panels reinforced by the ramie cloth without size were better than those of by the ramie cloth with size as shown in Fig.2 (a), (b) and (c). However, the tensile strength of the cloth with size shown in table 1 is higher than that of the cloth without size. In this point, the differences of the mechanical properties for the composites are mainly from the different interfacial bond strength. The size agents made from PVA (polyvinyl alcohol) and starch for textile process influenced the bond strength between fibers and the matrix. It would block the impregnation of the UP and then form some weak bond areas in composites. The yarns pulled out from the fractured surfaces could be observed during tensile test.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig2. Effect of the surface conditions of ramie fabric on the mechanical properties, (a) tensile strength, (b) bend strength, (c) shear strength

Influence of Fiber Volume Fraction

The test results indicated that the fiber volume fraction did not have remarkable effect on the

mechanical behaviors of ramie fabric composite. It seems to be true when the volume fraction increased from 31% to 53% that the shear strength measured had no significant change as shown in Fig.3. Moreover, no significant influence on the tensile strength was found with the fiber volume fraction varying from 40% to 56% as shown in Fig. 4. Therefore, the study shows that properties of ramie composites depend not only on the interphase conditions but on the intrinsic properties of the ramie fiber which are quite different from those of man-made fibers. This unexpected result may also imply that some concepts on relationship between mechanical properties of composite panel and fiber volume fraction applicable to conventional composites reinforced by artificial fibers seem to be not applicable directly to analyzing this new composite system. It should be mentioned that the results presented here are preliminary. Much more work needs to be done.

Fig.3 Effect of the fiber volume fraction on the shear strength

Fig.4 Effect of the fiber volume fraction on the tensile strength

Composite Morphology

Scanning electron microscopy of fractured surfaces of two kinds of composites was made to study the morphology and adhesion between the fiber and the matrix.

The scanning electron micrograph in Fig. 5 (a) shows a typical fracture surface of shear specimens of the composite reinforced by ramie cloth with size. It can be seen that there is a poor adhesion between fibers and UP matrix.

Fig. 5 (b) shows another typical fracture surface of the composite reinforced by ramie cloth without size. Compared to the micrographs in Fig. 5 (a) the fractured surfaces presented better adhesion between fibers and UP matrix.

Fig 5 SEM micrographs showing the adhesion quality of interface between fibers and matrix, (a) with size on the ramie fabric, (b) without size on the ramie fabric

SUMMARY

The mechanical properties tests including tensile and bend and shear were conducted with a new natural fiber composite materials ramie fabric composites. The effect of fiber surface condition and fiber volume fraction on the mechanical properties was investigated. The preliminary results show: (1) the composites reinforced by ramie fabric without the size on surface have higher tensile and bend and shear strength than those by the ramie fabric with the size on surface; (2) the fiber volume fraction has no significant influence on the tensile and shear strength. SEM observation indicated that the interfacial quality of the composite filled by ramie fabric without size is better than that of its counterpart.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work was supported by the Chinese National Natural Science Foundation and Shaanxi Province Science Research Project. The authors also acknowledge the the technical support given by the Electron Microscopy Lab of LNM, Institute of Mechanic, Chinese Academy of Sciences. Materials preparation and experiment assistant provided by Mr. Y.Y. Li are also much appreciated.

REFERENCES

1. Garkhail, S. Heijenrath, R., Oever, M. Vanden, Bos, H. And Peijs, T., "Natural-Fiber-Mat-Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites Based on Flax Fibers and Polypropylene", *Proceedings of the Eleventh International Conference on Composite Materials*, Gold Coast, Australia, July 14-18, 1997, Vol. II, PP. 794-803
2. Joseph, K. and Thomas, S., "Effect of Ageing on the Physical and Mechanical Properties of Sisal-Fiber-Reinforced Polyethylene Composites", *Journal of Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 53, 1995, PP. 99-110.
3. Gassan, J. and Bledzki, A.K., "Possibilities to improve the Properties of Natural Fiber Reinforced Plastics by Fiber Modification", *Processing of Eighth European Conference on Composite Materials Science, Technology and Application*, June 3-6, 1998, Naples, Italy, Vol. 2, PP. 111-126
4. Oksman, K. and Nilsson, P., "Thermoplastic Composites Based on Natural Fiber", *Processing of Eighth European Conference on Composite Materials Science, Technology and Application*, June 3-6, 1998, Naples, Italy, Vol. 2, PP. 133-140
5. Herrann, A. S. And Hanselka, "Composites with Biological Fiber-(e.g. Hemp-) and Matrix-Components", *Proceedings of the Symposium, BIOROHSTOFF HANF*, Frankfurt Main, Germany, March 2-5, 1995, PP. 383-391
6. Zheng, R., Xian, X.J., Yipp, W.M. and Shin, F.G., Analysis and Propertied of Jute / Epoxy Composite" (in Chinese), *ACTA MATERIAE COMPOSITAE SIMCA*, Vol. 12, 1995, PP. 18-25
7. Yang, G.C., Zeng, H.M. and Li, J.J., "Study of Sisal Fiber / Phenol Formaldehyde Resin Composite" (in Chinese), *Journal of Fiber Reinforced Plastic / Composites*, Vol. 3, 1997, PP. 12-14
8. Li, Z.D., "Cultivating Principle and Technique for Bast Fiber Plants" (in Chinese), *Shanghai Science and Technology Publish House*, 1980